

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT THOUGHT ECOTOURISM DEVELOPMENT AT TANJUNG PUTING NATIONAL PARK

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to analyze and quantify of the determinant factors to sustainable ecotourism development of Tanjung Puting National Park. Methods are survey and observation, using a questionnaire to obtain information related to both independent and dependent variables. Research location is in Tanjung Puting Park, Central Kalimantan Province, conducted in May – July 2019. The population in this study are both foreign tourists and domestic tourists who visited Tanjung Puting National Park. The data used primary and secondary. The samples carried through nonprobability sampling techniques, namely convenience sampling (Sugiono, 2002), the sample size was 250 respondents. Analysis tool that uses statistical analysis of test models Path Analysis the results showed (1) the Tourist Product and the Uniqueness of the Environment development significant influence on Tourist Visits and Length of Stay, (2) Tourist Product and Uniqueness of the Environment development variables to influence of Sustainable Ecotourism.

Keywords: Ecotourism, Sustainable Development, National Park.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of eco-tourism (ecotourism), as one of the tourism industry with the potential to increase the revenue of the country, especially in the last decade. Nesparnas 2001-2011 report states that in 2007, foreign exchange contributed ecotourism amounting to Rp 60 trillion and increased to Rp. 80 trillion in 2008, an increase of 33%. Contributions were obtained from tourist arrivals of 6.5 million people into the ecotourism area are scattered in various destinations in Indonesia. Ecotourism development that put forward the concept of environmental sustainability and the values of the local culture. Something that is logical from the concept of sustainable development, in which a variety of disciplines and approaches require careful planning, both physically and management (1) (2) (3). Thus the development of ecotourism should be able to improve the quality of human relations, improve the quality of life of local communities and maintain the quality of the environment (4). The development of the tourism sector both from the aspect of the number of tourist visits, as well as from the receipt aspect, has described how the tourism sector can be relied upon to encourage the economic growth of a region (5) (6) (7). Another thing that is not important of all it is a direct and indirect impact on the involvement of workers in various activities supporting tourism as a travel agent (travel agency), restaurants, travel managers, tour guides and so on (8, 9). Sustainable tourism development is a model of tourism development on a small scale, controlled, lasting (sustainable), tourism is a way to enjoy the life of local communities, and tourism related to ecology (10) (11). The concept of the development of tourism as it is one of the concepts of alternative tourism development (alternative tourism) where in it contains a pattern of sustainable development to prioritize environmental concerns and conservation

(ecological) (12) (13) (14, 15). Pariwisata sustainable development as development that focused on two things, namely the sustainability of tourism as an economic activity and consider tourism as an element of sustainable development policies more broadly. Thought Sharpley (2000), on the concept of sustainable development in principle refers to how the potential ecological utilized as an economic good with mendedapatkan good planning and involving the wider community to participate actively through a partnership that synergy. Central Kalimantan Province with an area of 153.364 km², as the third largest province in Indonesia and has a good potential for ecotourism because it has a high diversity of flora and fauna are unique. The biological potential of natural resources and the unique characteristic in natural ecosystems, has a great chance to be sold on the tourism market world. Relation to the impact caused by tourism activities in Central Kalimantan, the Central Bureau Statistics if Central Kalimantan Province in 2009, showed that in 2007 the number of workers involved in the system of tourism in Central Kalimantan (restaurant, travel agent, tour manager, tour guide) is as much 262 people rose to 356 people in 2008, or an increase of 35.9%. That means that how the tourism sector into a driving force to encourage local economic growth through the absorption of labor in various sectors of the tourism system. The condition of Ecosystem in Central Kalimantan which has potential and biodiversity is very high as well as unique. Tanjung Puting National Park as one of the national park which is owned by Central Kalimantan since the last few years was designed as an area of ecological economic value high enough to be developed as a tourist area, and since 2007 the Indonesian government to establish as a major destination nationwide to 33 in constellation of national tourism. Based on the potential that has a diversity of flora and fauna is quite high and has a unique ecosystem as well as the enactment of the first orang-utan rehabilitation center in Indonesia. The concept of regional planning and the development of ecotourism TNTP divided into four locations, namely in Tanjung Harapan, Pondok Tanggui, Pondok soar and Camp Leakey. In these locations tourism products that can be enjoyed by tourists is the uniqueness and diversity of flora and fauna as well as other attractions such as: wildlife observation, feeding orangutans, trekking, black water ecosystem, the river edge, and research station tropical forest plant, area camping ground, attractions Art and culture. Central Kalimantan tourism development, particularly the TanjungPuting National Park shows a significant development seen from the tourist traffic within the last ten years. Overview of the number of foreign and domestic tourist visits to the location of an object ecotourism Central Kalimantan on four years later as follows:

Table 1: Number of tourists to TanjungPuting National Park Year 2015-2018

No.	Year	Foreign	Domestic	Amount	Share (%)
1.	2015	9.767	2.797	12.564	
2.	2016	8.927	6.184	15.091	16,7
3.	2017	15.163	9.975	25.138	40,1
4.	2018	18.163	10.449	29.283	14.2
	Total	52.671	29.405	82.076	

Source: Annual Report 2015 TNTP Hall. Description: TNTP = TanjungPuting National Park

Table 1 shows that the number of tourist arrivals and domestic flights ecotourism TNTP area during the period 2015-2018 increased from 12,564 people in 2015 to 29. 283 people in 2018. The increase in visits from the number seems quite good, but in terms of percentage increase annually decrease. In the first year (2015 - 2016) share of tourist arrivals seen in the percentage of 16.7 %, increase to 40.1% on 2017 and decrease to 14.2% on 2018. Along 2015-2018 the percentage of tourist arrivals are 42.9%. These figures show that an increasing number of tourists visiting to Tanjung Putting National Park quite significant, so the percentage increase on four years later is linier.

Tanjung Puting National Park, the performance achievements in terms of tourist arrivals mostly depend on the supply of tourist product like: demonstration plot of medicinal plants at Pesalat spot, Feeding Orangutan at Pondok Tanggui and Camp Leakey, Research Station at Pondok Ambung, Conservation of Turtle and White Sand Beach at Buluh Besar River. Actually the performance number of tourist visits to TNTP is low, due to accessibility factors and the position of the city of Palangka Raya and Pangkalan Bun is not the entrance of foreign tourists, as well as lack of information and not maximal promotion, packaging tourism products (attractions, facilities and infrastructure) are still minimal.

According to the tour, et al, that the length of stay of tourists in the area attractions are influenced by economic variables such as: a limited budget, tourist earnings and the price of tourism products. Smith and Choy stated that their motivation for tourists to visit the tourist destination due to the availability of facilities and infrastructure are interrelated, management and good organization, so it's not just tourism products which provide comfort but management itself already gives comfort for every visitor. Furthermore Ryan and Kim et al states that tourists who visit an object for their factors (push factor) and pull factors (pull factor), where the pull factors are tourist attractions, the existence of water resources and the sea, beauty mountains, and local culture. In line with the statement Irawan that the travel products (natural and artificial attractions and tourist facilities) if packaged properly, enhanced, will affect tourists visiting tourist attraction in Central Kalimantan. This opinion is reinforced by the statement of Smith (1994), which says that there is a relationship between the tourism product with the number of tourist visits, as the attractions and tourist facilities is fundamental to attract tourists to visit a tourist attraction. Furthermore, according to Holloway and Murphy (1989) asserts that outlines the components of tourism products can be grouped into six sections: attractions, accommodation, catering, transport and other infrastructure. So the tourism product offered an attraction can be a driver of a person residing elsewhere to visit the attraction (Bukart & Medlik, 1981. Cooper, 1993).

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in the study is a survey method and observation, using a questionnaire as an instrument to obtain information related to the study variables (primary data). The unit of analysis or as the population is foreign and domestic tourists who visit TNTP the samples were done through techniques nonprobability sampling, ie Convenience sampling with accidental sampling method against any foreign tourists and the archipelago are found and deemed worthy

to serve as respondents based on predetermined criteria, can be defined as samples. The amount of attention to a reference sample Fraenkel and Wallen, Payangan is as much as 250 respondents. A total of 170 respondents from foreign and 80 respondents from domestic tourists. Secondary data as supportive data obtained from the office of Central Bureau Statistic West Kotawaringin, Department of Culture and Tourism of the Central Kalimantan Province, Central Office Tanjung Puting National Park and the Natural Resources Conservation Center (BKSDA) Central Kalimantan Province.

Analysis of data using statistical models Path Analysis Test, to see the relationship marketing variables travel with the travel demand using Amos software version 18 (Analysis of Moment Structure) and SPSS version 10. The analysis of the data by using the formulation function as follows:

$$Y1 = F(X1, X2)$$

$$Y2 = F(X1, X2, Y1)$$

The Reduce form calculation process:

$$Y1 = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X1 + \alpha_2 X2 + \epsilon_1$$

$$Y2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X1 + \beta_2 X2 + \beta_3 Y1 + \epsilon_2$$

$$Y2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X1 + \beta_2 X2 + \beta_3 (\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X1 + \alpha_2 X2 + \epsilon_1) + \epsilon_2$$

$$Y2 = (\beta_0 + \alpha_0 \beta_3) + (\beta_1 + \alpha_1 \beta_3) X1 + (\beta_2 + \alpha_2 \beta_3) X2 + (\epsilon_1 \beta_3 + \epsilon_2).$$

Where:

α_1 = direct influence on the frequency of travel products tourist arrivals

α_2 = the direct influence of the environmental uniqueness Frequency tourist arrivals

β_1 = direct influence on the travel products Length of Stay

β_2 = direct influence of environment on the uniqueness Length of Stay

$\alpha_1 \beta_3$ = direct effect on the tourism product through Frequency Length of Stay Travelers

$\alpha_2 \beta_3$ = direct influence of the environmental uniqueness through Frequency Length of Stay Travelers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several issues About Tourism

The development of tourism is quite rapidly to become one of the industry sector (Naisbit, 1994) have estimated that starting in 2000 the tourism sector will be the world's largest industry and accounts for the global economy. In line with the Naisbit (1994) statement, the World Tourism Organisation (WTO) in 2010 reported that the number of global travelers will increase to 1.018 million people with foreign exchange earnings of US\$ 3.4 trillion, investment amounted to 10.7% of the world tourism capital of the world, and employment opportunities

as many as 204 million people (Yoety, 2008). The amount of the contribution of the tourism sector to the global economy as a result of high levels of and travel the world. And travel the world has experienced a shift, such as the report on the world conference on the environment (Globe'90) in Vancouver Canada, mentions that the traveler behavior patterns experienced a shift from mass tourism (mass tourism) to special interest tours (special tourism). Shifting traveler behavior according Suradnya is an evolution that leads to a paradigm shift about the destination of choice, in the context of sustainable tourism where the main goal is how to optimize readiness unique destination and experience through the development of ecotourism. Sustainable tourism is synonymous with ecotourism is possible to develop optimally or will not encounter any significant obstacles, for their support of natural resource potential is enormous.

As a multi-dimensional phenomenon, tourism has been cultivating the image of adventure, romantic and exotic places, and when viewed from the context of an activity. Bagyono says that tourism is part of the elements of the business, health, social, political, religious and other interests, curiosity, adding to the experience or learning). Meanwhile Smith and Gun (1994), considers that the historical nature of tourism studies, and evolving towards a descriptive geographic studies and thereafter until the study of travel from the aspects of history and ideology. Furthermore, John and Murphy states that tourism can be approached through the concept of economic growth, so that tourism can be considered as an industry. Likewise, John and Murphy in his study has incorporated elements of the economy through the production of goods and services that can be extracted from the development of tourism.

The results of the study tour as economic growth, certainly in the course of time will involve and encourage the development of other sectors so that in turn drives the national economy (Yoety, 1996 and Wahab, 2003). For countries that have natural resources like Indonesia, in recent years has developed, even relying on the tourism sector as one sector foreign exchange earner. Sekartjakrarini (2004) also says that there are key factors that influence the development of ecotourism, among others: the objects and attractions, infrastructure, institutional, transportation or accessibility, accommodation, facilities and services as well as the implications for the environment and the economy. Gufran concluded that the main factor for the development of ecotourism is to include: (a) the safety factor, (b) a conservation factor, uniqueness factor objects and factors of tourist attraction, in addition there is a supplementary factor which is also important to note is the management (institutional), accessibility and minimum impact factor.

Ecotourism and Sustainable Tourism Development

Sustainable development goals outlined Seragaldin (1996) in "a triangle framework", that the development of the tourism industry geared towards sustainable tourism, which is one form of ecological tourism (ecotourism). The potential of natural resources large enough they form a tourist area that has a variety of attractions unique has been offering travel-based nature (nature-based-tourism) including eco-tourism (ecotourism), travel adventure (adventure tourism), and nautical tourism (marine tourism). Gufran states that there are some minimum criteria in the development of ecotourism, namely: (a) the preservation and uniqueness ODTW

including the conservation of flora, fauna, natural beauty and maintain the uniqueness of the local culture, (b) the accessibility to and within the region, or the facilities and infrastructures of transport, (c) safety when traveling and insurance, (d) the minimum infrastructure like the rest area (gazebo), toilet, (e) the institution and regulation, (f) business travel (travel agents, travel writer), (g) the relationship with ODTW other, (h) minimum impact on the environment, (i) the promotion, (10) tourism carrying capacity, (j) the empowerment of the community, (k) the economic contribution (the amount of tourist spending), (l) education.

Sustainable tourism development having an positive impact on the surrounding communities in the form of the flow of money from tourists to local people who have access to job opportunities through ecotourism activities such as interpreters, tour guides, transportation providers, providers of accommodation, food and beverage providers, sales of souvenirs. All of the multiplier effect, in turn, increase the income of local communities. But on the other hand, the development of ecotourism is also possible negative impacts such as environmental degradation and changes in social and cultural conditions. By understanding the main elements of the concept of eco-tourism development, then in this case ecotourism offer the concept of low-invest-high value for natural resources and the environment, while making it as a powerful tool for public participation to be actively involved in the process of sustainable tourism development.

Ecotourism development in protected areas such as national parks become the object of tourist attraction (ODTW) using a separate approach to the conservation and utilization, but in practice is more focused on "preservation". Ecotourism is a form of travel that is managed with conservation approach, as an attempt to preserve the natural resouces utilization for the present and the future. This concept is in line with the definition made by the International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources, that conservation is man's attempt to take advantage of the biosphere by trying to deliver great results and sustainable for present and future generations. Thus that ecotourism should be able to guarantee the preservation of the environment as a form of implementation of the conservation objectives as stated United Nations Environmental Program in Fandeli, namely: (a) maintain the positive process ecological still life support systems; (b) protect biodiversity; (c) ensure the preservation and utilization of species and ecosystems. Efforts to preserve the environment, the development of ecotourism does not exploit nature, but only use the services of nature and society to meet the needs of the knowledge, physical and psychological rating, so it can be said that ecotourism destination not to sell but to sell philosophy.

Further Fandeli says that the product of ecotourism is the beauty, uniqueness, authenticity and knowledge (knowledge) that is located in an area, even ecotourism sell products that are experience (experience). Ecotourism as a form of tourism with conservation activities that rely on will be beneficial ecologically, socially and economically, local communities and ensure the preservation of natural resources and sustainable. Ecotourism emphasis on environmental sustainability provide positive understanding for tourists visiting so the presence of tourists in the national park area are partly responsible for the cleanliness of the environment, not destroy vegetation, no soil erosion and environmental conditions remain subdued well, and thus where

travelers have made a significant contribution through the understanding of the importance of environmental sustainability for the existence of ecotourism in Madhav National Park can be sustained.

The development of ecotourism in the context of tourism more emphasis on eco-development which include: (a) use of natural resources; (B) the use of appropriate technology; (C) the utilization of social and political capability of local communities. So as to achieve sustainability of ecotourism, some suggestions and concepts that need to be considered are: (a) respect the integrity and existence of ecosystems; (B) local participation; and (c) provide economic opportunities for local communities. Relation to the concept of sustainable development is the basis for the development of ecotourism in Indonesia, covering five basic principles, namely: (a) the preservation; (B) education; (C) tourism; (D) the economy; and the participation of local communities. By understanding some of the issues related to ecotourism portrait, it can be concluded that the development of sustainable ecotourism has the scope of a complex and multidimensional, and it relates to one another.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Variable travel products and environmental uniqueness of this research is positioned as an independent variable and a variable number of visits and length of stay of tourists which is positioned as the dependent variable. Relation to the factors that influence the development of ecotourism sustainable, is a variable component of tourism products that include several tourist attractions, such as: feeding the orang-utan, the river edge, wildlife observation, tracking, conservation, art and cultural attractions and tourist infrastructure such as transport, accommodation (homestay, motel), restaurants, souvenir. While the variable component of the uniqueness of the environment includes the diversity of flora and fauna, the presence of black water in the ecotourism area TNTP. Variable components described visits by tourists visiting frequency and length of stay variable described by how long the international and domestic tourists stayed in ecotourism TNTP role in every visit. Here is presented the results of testing the relationship between aspects of the supply side represented by the variable and unique tourism products to the environmental aspects of the demand side represented by a variable frequency tourist visits and length of stay of tourists. Here is presented the results of the analysis of the relationship between variables and unique tourism products to variable frequency environment tourist visits and length of stay of tourists.

Influence of Tourism Product Development of the Frequency of Visits Travelers

Path analysis results indicate that the Developing tourism products significantly influence the frequency of tourist visits, the calculation results show the value of CR amounted to 4.013 and $p = 0.0000$, and the estimated value of 0.3367. This means that if the tourism product consists of feeding the orangutans, the river edge, wildlife observation, tracking, conservation, art and cultural attractions and tourist infrastructure to be upgraded and quality by one unit, then the frequency of tourist arrivals will increase by 0.3367 times. Tourism product development is done by increasing the variety of tourism products (attractions and amenities) gave an indirect role on the length of stay of tourists through the many tourists visit frequency. The results

showed that the development of tourism products has been quite formed preferences foreign tourists and domestic tourists to visit the tourist area of Tanjung Puting National Park in Central Kalimantan. Motivation for tourists to visit the tourist destination due to the availability of facilities and infrastructure are interrelated, management and good organization, so it's not just tourism products which provide comfort but management itself already gives comfort for every visitor (16) (17) (18). Travelers who visit an object for their factors (push factor) and pull factors (pull factor), where the pull factors are tourist attractions, the existence of water resources and the sea, the beauty of the mountains and the local culture (19) (20). In line with what was achieved in this study, that the tourist products (attractions natural and man-made as well as tourist facilities) if packaged properly, enhanced, will affect tourists who visit the ecotourism area TNTP Central Kalimantan (21) (22). Furthermore, there is a relationship between the tourism product with the number of tourist visits, as the attractions and tourist facilities is fundamental to attract tourists to visit a tourist attraction (23) (24). Outlines the components of tourism products can be grouped into six sections: attractions, accommodation, catering, transport and other infrastructure (25). So the tourism product offered an attraction can be a driver of a person residing elsewhere to visit the attraction (26). Thus the development of tourism products indicated by the addition of the components on each attraction,

Influence of Tourism Product Development to variable Length Of Stay:

The analysis showed that the development of tourism products significantly affect the long-stay travelers, where it is indicated by the value of CR at 7.8049, $p = 0.0000$ and the estimated value of 0.2766. This means that if the tourism product consists of feeding the orangutans, the river edge, wildlife observation, tracking, conservation, art and cultural attractions and tourist infrastructure and its quality upgraded by one unit, then the length of stay of tourists in the ecotourism area TNTP will increase by 0.2766 time. Tourism product development by showing a unique tourism product is certainly a capital base and become the preference of tourists and Vishnu spend more time in the region ODTW to be able to enjoy all the natural attractions (natural attraction) offered by the organizer. Ecotourism products in the form of sight freelance and availability of accommodation facilities such as homestays and camping area has been the preference of tourists to visit and stay longer in the area because tourists feel comfort during the tour and can enjoy the scenery on a freelance basis, The behavior of tourists who visit the ecotourism area is a reflection of a trip to the area pristine, relatively undisturbed or contaminated with the objective of studying, admiring and enjoying the scenery, wildlife, flora and fauna and local culture carefully and long (27).

There are two fundamental things, and the motivation for tourists to stay long in the tourism destination that geographic factors and factors of the country of destination (28). TNTP geographical position relatively far from the entrance of tourists and requires a relatively long travel time, becoming a challenge for the management of ecotourism TNTP order to visit and travelers staying a long time longer in the area. The issue rating level of satisfaction when traveled at an object is affected by the quality of tourism products and services of other tourist services enjoyed by tourists in national parks (29). Empirical conditions in ecotourism TNTP shows that the quality of tourism products, especialytourist attraction of natural and artificial

are relatively good, but the product other tourist such as: accommodation, transportation and food and beverages not provide satisfaction for tourists, which in turn affects the duration of tourists were in the area TNTP ecotourism. The reason is in line with the opinion, there are three basic aspects as the driving factor tourists to visit the national park that is an object of natural resources support, information and convenience and accessibility of facilities and transportation. In line with the reality on the ground that the tourist attraction TNTP has fulfilled one of the basic aspects of these are natural resources, in terms of the diversity of flora and fauna as a natural product that lets can be a motivating factor for tourists and Vishnu to linger in the area of the object. However, accessibility and transportation factors have not providing certainty for travelers to more quickly get to the object because of the poor quality of road infrastructure.

Influence Development of Environmental Uniqueness of the Frequency of Tourist Visits:

The results of the analysis of the relationship between variables indicate that the development of the environmental uniqueness significant negative effect on the length of stay of tourists. Where it is shown by the CR value of 2.1338, $p = 0.0329$ and the estimated value of 0.1846. This means that if the uniqueness of the environment in the form of a diversity of flora and fauna as well as the existence of black water quality improvement by one unit, then the frequency of tourist arrivals and domestic flights TNTP ecotourism will increase by 0, 1846 times. An object region that has a unique environment, like ecotourism TNTP basically have strong competitiveness against other destinations. The destinations that have good fundamental environmental quality will show its existence and the competition as a destination chosen by tourists to visit (30). The existence of the National Park as one area that gets serious attention in terms of conservation of environmental functions, to in turn can be used as an ecotourism area economic value. The concept of the modern conservation efforts should contain utilization while maintaining environmental sustainability. One package is environmentally sustainable strategy is to: (1) strengthen the capacity of local planning to include conservation aspects into spatial planning; (2) the rationalization of rights over resources such as land rights; and (3) the development of the local area. The development of ecotourism in forest areas through conservation concept aims to maintain the quality and integrity of ecosystems leads to the development of ecotourism environmentally sound and sustainable. Thus that maintain and improve the quality of the environment an ecotourism area, as well as TNTP will encourage and be a deciding factor for tourists to visit each other periodically to the region in question.

The study results Kelkit et alfor a potential national park Gallipoli in Turkey, which examines the relationship between the uniqueness of the environment with the development of ecotourism through tourist visits. Kelkit et al suggested that the uniqueness of the National Park neighborhood Gallipoli Turkey is a tourism product that can be enjoyed by tourists who visit the park. The findings in the field were reinforced by data from annual reports of Tanjung Puting National Park Office in 2015 and the Department of Tourism and Culture of Central Kalimantan 2014, showed that the average frequency of visits of tourists to ecotourism TNTP is 3-4 times. Finally, it can be concluded that tourism development can be realized by

maintaining the uniqueness of the environment which belongs to a neighborhood, because of it's uniquely a tourist area will encourage tourists to witness the region.

Influence Development of Environmental uniqueness to Length of Stay:

The analysis showed that the unique development environment significantly affect the long-stay travelers, where it is indicated by a CR value of -2.3734 and $p = 0.0176$, and the estimated value of -0.0868. This means that if the uniqueness of the environment is raised one unit, then the long stay of tourists decreased by 0.0868 hours. These results demonstrate empirically unique development environment is one determinant in increasing tourist traffic in Central Kalimantan province. The duration of time spent by tourists to enjoy travel packages in a conservation area which has a unique ecosystem was influenced by economic variables such as limited budget, income and prices. Furthermore Akama states that tourists who derive satisfaction while watching the attractions in the area treated with the object because the quality of attractions and variety of tourism services is maximized, thus pushing for a longer stay. Referring to the results of the study tour et al that the determinants of long-stay travelers in travel area economic factors (income), meaning that the larger tourist income the greater the chances for a longer stay in the tourist area. The findings in the field were reinforced by data from annual reports Tanjung Puting National Park Authority and the Department of Tourism and Culture of Central Kalimantan 2014, showed that the average length of stay of tourists in the tourist area TNTP is 2-3 nights. The findings in this study is in line with the statement Gokovali. U at.Al (2007), that the long duration of stay of tourists affected by the hospitality, education, income, experience, familiarity and daily expenses.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Noting the results of the analysis and discussion of sustainable development through the Development of Ecotourism in Tanjung Putting National Park in Central Kalimantan province, the conclusions can be drawn that development of tourism products (natural attractions and artificial attractions) significantly influence the frequency of visits and length of stay of tourists. Development of the uniqueness of the environment (flora and fauna as well as black water) significantly influence the frequency of visits and the length of stay tourist. Sustainable development can be achieved through the development of ecotourism in Tanjung Puting National Park, by improving the quality and variety of tourism products and environment uniqueness. Keeping Tanjung Puting National Park area as an ecotourism area by maintaining the function of existing ecosystems by maintaining natural conditions are unique. Improving of the travel attraction variations both natural and artificial. Improving tourism support infrastructure support such as accommodation, transport in the region, consumption (beverage) and the comfort of traveling.

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Appendix 1. Table: Testing Results Influence of Tourism Products, Environmental uniqueness of the frequency of visits and long stay travelers Based on research model

No.	Relationships between variables		Estimated	C.R	P	Result
	Independent	Dependent				
1.	Tourist Product (X1)	Frequency Visit Tourists (Y ₁)	0,3367	4,0213	0,0000	Signifikan
		Length Of Stay (Y2)	0,2766	7,8049	0,0000	Signifikan
2.	The uniqueness of the Environment (X ₂)	Frequency Visit Tourists (Y ₁)	0,1846	2,1338	0,0329	Signifikan
		Length Of Stay (Y2)	-0,0868	-2,3734	0,0176	Signifikan

Source: Primary Data 2019. Ket: * = significant of 0, 05 percent

Appendix 2: Figure Scheme of Testing Results Independent Variables Influence on Dependent Variables

